

Agricultural University of Athens
Department of Agricultural Economics and Development
Laboratory of Informatics

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Assessing the Needs for Improvement of Higher Education in Digital Agriculture: A Questionnaire for Higher Education Institutions

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TALLHEDA

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the European Union

Objective

To provide comprehensive insights into the **current state** and **future needs** of Digital Agriculture (DA) education in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from **faculty members'** side of view.

Agenda

01

TALLHEDA Project

02

Methodology of the Research

03

Research Results

04

Conclusions

01

TALLHEDA Project

TALLHEDA is a Horizon Widera project that aims to build a new long-term Alliance for DA between agricultural **HEIs** from two widening countries, **Greece** and **Serbia**, with leading non-widening agricultural universities, and local and international stakeholders from **Belgium**.

01

TALLHEDA Background

Widening countries

Widening countries, such as **Greece** and **Serbia**, fall behind the European average in terms of investment in Research and Innovation as well as scientific excellence, with DA being a notable area of concern. HEIs in widening countries have the potential to significantly address this gap, but they require support to achieve excellence in DA education and research.

Non-widening country

On the contrary, HEIs in non-widening countries like **Belgium** have successfully developed ecosystems that promote close collaboration between HEIs, Digital Innovation Hubs, and industry, employing advanced digital technologies to benefit residents and businesses.

01

TALLHEDA Objectives

1

Identify **key areas** requiring transform, enhancement or support, to ensure that DA education aligns with the latest advancements and industry demands.

2

Foster **collaboration** and **innovation** in DA within HEIs across Europe, particularly in widening countries.

3

Establish a **culture of excellence** in DA education and research.

01

TALLHEDA in numbers

Funded by
the European Union

Project name:

TRANSFORMING ACCESS TO EXCELLENCE WITH SUCCESSFUL ALLIANCES
OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN DIGITAL AGRICULTURE

Project acronym:

TALLHEDA

Call:

HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-03

Granting authority:

European Research Executive Agency

Grant managed through EU Funding & Tenders Portal: Yes (eGrants)

Project starting date:

1 January 2024

Project end date:

30 June 2027

Project duration:

42 months

Maximum grant amount:

3 097 341.00

Greece

Belgium

Serbia

01

TALLHEDA Partners

01 TALLHEDA Partners

Three European universities partnered with other national and local actors in the agri-food domain, to form an alliance in the framework of the EU project TALLHEDA, in order to analyse the needs for reforming and updating HEI faculty members' offered courses and programmes to further facilitate and promote DA education.

**Agricultural University
of Athens, Greece**

**Univerzitet U Novom
Sadu, Serbia**

**Universiteit Gent,
Belgium**

02 Methodology of the Research

With a view to identifying the reform needs of HEIs in the area of DA, a comprehensive **questionnaire-based survey** was developed through a five-step systematic process.

01

Literature Review:

Identifying existing critical aspects related to DA education within HEIs

02

Objectives:

Posing research questions based on the identified critical aspects

03

Stakeholder Engagement:

Reviewing of the research questions by a group of stakeholders

04

Questionnaire:

Developing the final questionnaire

05

Distribution and Collection:

Distributing the questionnaire to HEI faculty members and collecting answers

02

Methodology of the Research

The primary **objective** of this research was to pinpoint key areas that require reform, enhancement, or additional support to ensure that DA education aligns with contemporary advancements and industry requirements.

In this context, the following research questions were developed:

- **RQ1.** Which **DA topics** have HEI faculty members already **incorporated** into their teaching?
- **RQ2.** To what extent do HEI faculty members **feel comfortable in integrating** DA topics into their courses?
- **RQ3.** How do they evaluate the **adequacy of resources** for DA at their HEI?
- **RQ4.** What is the **quality of teaching and research** in DA at their HEI compared to other well-recognized HEIs?
- **RQ5.** Which DA topics would they like to **incorporate more** into their teaching in the **future?**

03 Research Results

Participants' Demographics

- The survey, was conducted between **April and May 2024**, and was disseminated in the three universities.
- The sample consists of fifty (50) participants, namely eleven (11) from Belgium; twenty (20) from Greece; and nineteen (19) from Serbia.

03

Research Results

RQ1. Which DA topics have HEI faculty members **already incorporated** into their teaching?

- In the **sample**, most professors (18) have incorporated **sustainable agricultural practices and technologies** into their teaching.
- In the **non-widening country**, most of them (7) have incorporated **precision agriculture and smart farming technologies** into their teaching.
- In the **widening countries**, the majority of professors (11) has incorporated **sustainable agricultural practices and technologies** into their teaching.

03

Research Results

RQ2. To what extent do HEI faculty members **feel comfortable in integrating** DA topics into their courses?

- In the **sample**, most professors (30%) feel “Moderately comfortable” in integrating DA topics into their courses.
- In the **non-widening country**, the largest group, (45,45%), feel “Moderately comfortable”. There is a divide, with almost 55% feeling not at all comfortable up to moderately comfortable, and about 45% feeling comfortable or very comfortable.
- In the **widening countries**, responses vary but there also seems to be a divide, with about 56% feeling comfortable or very comfortable in integrating DA topics and 44% feeling moderately or slightly comfortable.

03

Research Results

RQ3. How do they evaluate the **adequacy of resources** for DA at their HEI?

- In the **sample**, the adequacy of educational materials and curriculum resources (40,82%), and laboratory and field equipment (41,67%) for DA are defined as “Fair”.
- In the **non-widening country**, the adequacy of educational materials and curriculum resources (63,64%) is defined as “Fair”. Laboratory and field equipment (90%) is defined between “Poor” and “Good”.
- In the **widening countries**, the adequacy of educational materials and curriculum resources (68,42%) is defined between “Poor” and “Fair”. The adequacy of laboratory and field equipment (44,74%) for DA is defined as “Fair”.

Overall

Non-widening country

Widening countries

03 Research Results

RQ4. How do they believe the **quality of teaching and research** in DA at their HEI compares to that of other well-recognized HEIs?

- In the **sample**, most professors (47,92%), based on their experiences and observations, believed that the quality of teaching and research in DA at their HEIs compares to that of other well-recognized HEIs, i.e., as “Same quality”.
- In the **non-widening country**, 63,64% believes that the quality is the same.
- In the **widening countries**, 41,03% believes that the quality is the same.

Overall

Non-widening country

Widening countries

03

Research Results

RQ5. Which DA topics would they like to **incorporate more** into their teaching in the **future**?

- In the **sample**, the majority of professors (10) would like to incorporate **blockchain for supply chain transparency and management** into their teaching in the future.
- Exactly the same is observed in the **widening countries**.
- In the **non-widening country**, most professors (4) would like to incorporate **agricultural robotics and automation** in their teaching in the future.

04

Conclusions

- Enhancing DA education is very important for HEIs.
- **Sustainable agricultural practices, precision agriculture and smart farming technologies** are the most prominent DA topics that HEI faculty members have already incorporated into their teaching. In the future, most professors would like to incorporate **blockchain for supply chain transparency and management, as well as agricultural robotics and automation** into their curricula.
- Most professors do not feel comfortable in integrating DA topics into their courses.
- They evaluate the adequacy of resources for DA at their HEI as “Fair”.
- Future work will focus on increasing the research sample and incorporating students', farmers' and food companies' perspective.
- The findings reveal valuable insights to guide the development of strategies targeted at enhancing DA education in higher education environments, benefiting students, educators, and the broader agricultural sector. Towards this end collaboration in this critical field.

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

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